

Implementation of RFID based Object Tracking System

Anoop Niranjana, Ashwini Kumar Verma, Rajat Jhajhria

B.Tech Students, SRM University, Chennai, Tamilnadu, India. E-mail: ajeyasekar@yahoo.com

Abstract – Radio frequency identification and wireless sensor network are promising technologies for the modern world. Location tracking is one of important applications of RFID and WSN technologies. When building a location tracking system, for the purpose of achieving real time location, a large amount of RFID and WSN hardware is required. The proposed indoor tracking system based on RFID technology and wireless sensor network is able to accurately locate movable entities such as people, robots etc within a defined surface. In this paper, we implement an RFID based location tracking system using a zigbee network architecture which provides flexibility for system implementation and cost effectiveness for system maintenance. The system employs active RFID technology to estimate the location of users/objects and Zigbee to build a network for communication purposes. It can be used for various purposes such as asset management and object tracking and also person tracking.

Keywords: RFID, RFID Tags, IEEE 802.15.4, Location Tracking System, Zigbee, Wireless Sensor Network

I. Introduction

In today's world of service, safety and security, proper personnel monitoring is vital to ensuring a successful operation. In recent years, there has been considerable interest in developing location or position tracking systems. Generally, such systems can be classified into indoor and outdoor systems. For outdoor location tracking, the Global Positioning System (GPS) is the most commonly used technology. Essentially in GPS, a receiver uses satellite signals to estimate its position. Cellular Communications offer an alternative outdoor location tracking solution. Here, the communication signals transmitted between the base stations and the mobile terminals are used to estimate the location of a mobile terminal. However, GPS and cellular communications cannot be employed in an indoor environment and may not work well in urban areas because signal reception can be affected by tall buildings.

So there has been considerable interest in developing a location or position tracking system for observing persons or objects on the move and supplying a timely ordered sequence of respective location data to a model e.g. capable of depicting motion on a display. Now a building system can be of various types like tracking in virtual space, tracking in real world etc. Generally, a tracking system is developed based on the area of application such as an indoor or an outdoor location tracking system.

For outdoor location tracking, the Global Positioning System (GPS) is the most commonly used technology. For indoor location tracking system [3][4], Wi-Fi and RFID are two major technologies that can be used. Wi-Fi based solution requires not only Wi-Fi based

infrastructure but also Wi-Fi supported user devices, which may be costly under certain circumstances, For example, a Wi-Fi based solution may not be cost-effective for tracking the location of objects or the locations of a large number of users without Wi-Fi devices. RFID can provide an alternative solution to the use of Wi-Fi. Compared with Wi-Fi devices, RFID tags are cheaper and can provide functions more cost effectively. Unlike Wi-Fi based system, RFID based location tracking system requires additional equipment.

In this paper, RFID based object location tracking system is implemented. All the RFID readers are considered as node and is connected to at least one other RFID reader to form a Wireless Sensor Network. With the use of Zigbee protocol, the network is formed easily and new nodes can be joined using a simple procedure.

II. Related Work

In day to life, people are very busy with their hectic schedule and a lot of work has to be done in a limited period of time. It is very difficult task to keep track of several consignments, packages, people etc and it requires lot of man power to track them. There are possibilities of failing to keep track of few so that a system is developed to keep track of people and objects. These systems make use of RFID technology for identifying and tracking the object and people. A P2P network with RFID readers is formed based on Zigbee and communication between them is established using 2.4GHz Zigbee protocol. In [1] a P2P network architecture, system setup and maintenance are proposed. The core components of the systems include active RFID tag, a prototype of Zigbee controller, and three prototypes of zigbee readers. Zigbee controller contains a zigbee module and connects with a

computer. The zigbee reader is meant for collecting RF data. It contains both zigbee module and RFID module. An active RFID reader with zigbee communication protocol serves as a node in the P2P network [2]. It includes three major elements: Master, node and tag. A tag is a 2.4GHz active tag which is attached to a tracking object. Each node is an active RFID reader that communicates with the tags and the master. The master is a gateway that works as backend server. It is connected to the computer and performs data collection and network management. The tags communicate with nodes using RF packets while nodes communicate with the master using Zigbee packets. When the nodes transfer an RF packet to the master, the nodes have to repack the RF packet into a Zigbee packet.

Zigbee is a specification for a suite of high level communication protocols used to create personal area networks built from small, low power digital radios. Zigbee is based on IEEE 802.15.4 standard. Though its low power consumption limits transmission distances to 10-100 meters line of sight, depending on power output and environmental characteristics, zigbee devices can transmit data over long distances by passing data through a mesh network of intermediate devices to reach more distance. The zigbee network layer natively supports both star and tree networks and generic mesh networking. Every network has one coordinator device, tasked with its creation, the control of its parameters and basic maintenance. Zigbee builds on the physical layer and media access control defined in IEEE 802.15.4 for low rate WPAN. The specification includes four additional key components: Network layer, Application layer, Zigbee device object (ZDO) and manufacturer defined application objects which allow for customaries. ZDO are responsible for a number of tasks including keeping track of device roles, manage requests to join a network as well as device discovery and security.

RFID reader board is a 125KHz RF transmitter and receiver, featuring EM4095 controller chip. The reader has three main functions: Energizing demodulation and decoding. Reader is connected to microcontroller of PC for encoding the data read from RFID tags. An RFID reader's function is to interrogate RFID tags. A reader contains an RF module which acts as both a transmitter and receiver of radio frequency signals. The transmitter consists of an oscillator to create the carrier frequency: A Modulator to impinge data commands upon this carrier signal and an amplifier to boost the signal enough to awaken the tag. The receiver has a demodulator to extract the returned data and also contains an amplifier to strengthen the signal for processing. A microprocessor forms the control unit which employs an operating system and memory to filter and store the data.

The tag contains electronically stored information. Some tags are powered by electromagnetic induction from magnetic fields produced near the reader. Some

types collect energy from the interrogating radio waves and act as a passive transponder. Other types have a local power source such as a battery and may operate at hundreds of meters from the reader. Unlike a barcode, the tag does not necessarily need to be within line of sight of the reader and may be embedded in the tracked object.

An RFID tag is composed of a minuscule microchip and antenna. RFID tags can be passive or active and come in a wide variety of sizes and shapes. An active tag has an on-board battery and periodically transmits its ID signal. A battery assisted passive (BAP) has a small battery on board and is activated when in the presence of an RFID reader. A passive tag is cheaper and smaller because it has no battery; instead the tag uses the radio energy transmitted by the reader. However to operate a passive tag, it must be illuminated with a power level roughly a thousand times stronger than for signal transmission. The RFID tags contain at least two parts: an integrated circuit for storing and processing information, modulating and demodulating a radio frequency signal, collecting DC power from the incident reader signal and other specialized functions and an antenna for receiving and transmitting the signal. The tag information is stored in a non-volatile memory. The RFID tag includes either fixed or programmable logic for processing the transmission and sensor data respectively.

Communication between the RFID reader and tags occurs wirelessly and therefore does not require a line of sight between devices. An RFID reader can read through most anything with the exception of conductive materials like water and metal but with modifications and positioning even these can be overcome.

III. Proposed System

The objective of this paper is to implement the RFID based object tracking system for a large organization. Every member in the organization carries an ID card embedded with an RFID tag. Each RFID tag has a unique ID that identifies the particular object in the organization. The working staffs are also considered as objects. RFID readers placed in different places of the organization sense the RFID tag, read the data and transmit to the central system that uploads the location of the object into the online server. It is shown in Fig 1.

After a network is set up, the node initially stays in the idle mode. To start identifying the tags, the master sends a "Start Read" command which is propagated to every node. Once a node receives the command, it moves from idle mode to listening mode. During the listening mode, a node listens to RF data from the RFID tag and measures the RSSI value. Periodically, each node will pass the tag information to the master through the P2P network. Having obtained all of the tag information from the P2P network, the master performs a distance estimation and location estimation.

Fig. 1. Architecture of RFID based Object Tracking System

IV. Conclusion and Future Work

The implementation of RFID based object tracking system makes use of active RFID technology for identifying and tracking staffs and objects in an organization. A P2P network with RFID readers is formed based on Zigbee. In other words, the readers communicate using the 2.4 GHz zigbee protocol. The testing of this system gives a successful result of reading the data from the active RFID tags through the RFID readers to the central database within a range of approximately 10 meters.

References

- [1] Felix C.P. Hui, Henry, C. B. Chan, S.H. Fung, "RFID based Location Tracking System using a Peer-to-Peer Network Architecture", International Multi Conference of Engineer and Computer Scientist, IMECS, Hong Kong, 2014.
- [2] Bolivar Torres et al "Integration of RFID reader to a Wireless Sensor Network and its use to identify an individual carrying RFID tags", Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico.
- [3] P. Chen "A cellular based Mobile Location Tracking System" IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference, 1999.
- [4] R. Bajaj, S.L. Ranawera, D.P. Agrawal, "GPS: Location Tracking Technology", IEEE Computer, Vol. 35(4), pp. 92-94, 2002.